

In vitro genotoxic study of β -asarone in human peripheral blood lymphocytes

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Abstract : Present study was carried out to ascertain whether β -asarone, a constituent of herbal medicinal oil exert genotoxic effects in human peripheral blood lymphocytes (PBL). For this study human PBL from six healthy human male volunteers were treated with 208 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ of β -asarone and leukocyte binucleate assay was performed. The results obtained suggest that β -asarone did not increase the incidence of micronucleated cells in PBL but mitomycin-C used as positive control had increased the incidence of micronucleated cells. Thus, our findings revealed that β -asarone did not have genotoxic or mutagenic effects for the tested dose.

Keywords : β -Asarone, *Acorus calamus*, micronucleus, mitomycin-C.

Introduction

β -Asarone (*cis*-isomer of 2,4,5-trimethoxy-1-propenylbenzene) is a constituent of oil derived from the dried rhizome of *Acorus calamus* which is used as herbal medicine. Percentage of β -asarone content in the rhizome oil depends on ploidy condition of the plant. The oil extracted from the tetraploid variety of *A. calamus* rhizome contains up to 95 to 96% β -asarone as a major component, on the other hand oil from the European or triploid form contains less than 10% of β -asarone. A diploid form of the plant contains virtually no asarone¹. The rhizome oil is strong, fragrant, pungent and aromatic, so it is used as flavouring agent. The rhizome containing β -asarone is used in traditional medicine to treat diabetes². A very recent study by Geng *et al.*, have shown β -asarone as a potential candidate for development as a therapeutic agent to manage cognitive impairment associated with conditions such as Alzheimer's disease³. Beta asarone also exhibits many biological activities like antimicrobial, antioxidant, anthelmintic and spasmolytic activity. But β -asarone was found to be hepatocarcinogenic by researchers in the preweanling mouse model and also oil of calmus containing β -asarone was reported to be an intestinal carcinogen in rats^{4,5}. As a consequence of these findings, the use of β -asarone is restricted to 1 ppm in alcoholic beverages and snack foods⁶. In human the maximum intake of β -asarone from food and alcoholic beverages can be restricted to be approximately 115 $\mu\text{g/day}$ i.e. about 2

$\mu\text{g/kg}$ body weight/day. But most of the biological activity of *Acorus calamus* is considered due to presence of β -asarone. Thus, genotoxic assay of β -asarone was chosen for the study.

Results and discussion

In human male peripheral blood a statistically non-significant increased micronucleus (MN) frequency was observed in the β -asarone treated cells at 48 h (5.1) sampling times compared with the control (4.6) and thereby it is decreasing at 96 h.

And also a small decrease in the values was seen at 72 and 96 h of PBL (Table 1). No other differences were observed in human PBL. But mitomycin-C exposure to the human male peripheral blood was showing the highly significant percentage of MN when compared with vehicle control at the same time point (Fig. 2).

Fig. 1. (a) Binucleated cell, (b) tetranucleated cell, (c) binucleated cell with micronuclei.

Table 1. Incidence of binucleated micronuclei in the peripheral blood of human male at various times after administration of a single dose of β -asarone

Treatment	Total MN frequency/1000 binucleate cells			
	24 h	48 h	72 h	96 h
Vehicle control	2.5 \pm 0.54	4.6 \pm 0.81	3.5 \pm 0.54	2.6 \pm 0.81
β -Asarone	2.3 \pm 0.51	5.1 \pm 0.40	3.3 \pm 0.51	2.5 \pm 0.54
Mitomycin-C	4.5 \pm 0.54*	11.1 \pm 0.40***	6.5 \pm 0.54*	6.1 \pm 0.40***

Values are presented as mean \pm SD, $n = 6$; *** $p < 0.001$ compared with vehicle control alone.

Fig. 2. The effect of β -asarone on binucleated micronuclei in peripheral blood. The incidence of micronuclei in binucleated PBC of human male is shown for various sampling times after administration of a single dose of β -asarone, vehicle control and mitomycin-C. Data represents mean \pm SD for six healthy human males treated with vehicle control, β -asarone and mitomycin-C. Statistical analysis was conducted using Student's t -test. (a - control vs mitomycin-C, * $p \leq 0.05$, ** $p \leq 0.01$ *** $p \leq 0.001$ compared with vehicle control).

Interestingly a similar result was reported in human lymphocytes treated with 107 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ of isomer mixture containing 70% β -asarone in the presence of metabolic activation. A small increase in sister chromatid exchange was recorded which was not significant. But in the absence of metabolic activation no effects were observed⁷. However, in another study it has been reported that a *trans* form of asarone induces sister chromatid exchange both in murine bone marrow *in vivo* and in human lymphocytes *in vitro*⁸. The results show that 208 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ β -asarone is neither a genotoxic nor a mutagen for the normal cellular mechanisms. However, further studies will be much needed to know and explore the side effects of the β -asarone on prolong or chronic exposure.

Experimental

Chemicals : β -Asarone and mitomycin-C were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich (USA), RPMI 1640 from

Gibco (India); Phytohemagglutinin from Invitrogen (India); Dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO), Fetal Bovine Serum (FBS), Penicillin, Streptomycin, Geimsa stain were obtained from Himedia (India).

Leukocyte culture and micronucleus assay : Six healthy human male volunteers blood sample was chosen for the study. For the determination of β -asarone effects in PBL, venous blood was drawn in sterile condition from each subject and whole culture were set up in the triplicates by adding 0.6 ml of heparinized blood to 6 ml of RPMI 1640 medium, supplemented with 1.2 ml of foetal bovine serum, antibiotics (penicillin and streptomycin), 208 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ of isomer mixture containing 70% β -asarone along with vehicle (DMSO) and the lymphocytes were stimulated with 4% phytohemagglutinin. The same was done for vehicle control and mitomycin-C. For micronucleus assay, the cultures were incubated at 37 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ for 96 h. Binucleated cells were accumulated by adding cytochalasin-B at a final concentration of 6 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ after initiation of culture following to 24 h, 48 h, 72 h and 96 h. At the end of the incubation time, the cells were collected by centrifugation at 1000 rpm for 5 min. Cells were washed once in RPMI 1640 medium and then a mild hypotonic treatment was given for 3–5 min at room temperature. The cells were then centrifuged at 1000 rpm for 3 min and fixed with a Carnoy's fixative. The fixation step was repeated twice. Slides were prepared, air dried and stained with giemsa. A total of 1000 binucleated cells with well defined cytoplasm were examined for each individual on coded slides for the micronucleus assay. The MN was examined according to the procedure described by Fenech⁹. The distribution of binucleated cells with micronucleus (BNMN) and the total micronucleus obtained among the individuals studied were compared with the normal distribution by means of the Kolmogorov-Smirnov test of goodness-of-fit. None of them deviated signifi-

cantly from normality, so a parametric test (the student *t*-test in this case) was used for statistical analysis of the results. To determine the percentage of cells with 1, 2, 3 and >4 nuclei a minimum of 500 cells were scored. A nuclear division index (NDI) was calculated according to the formulae $NDI = (M1 + 2M2 + 3M3 + 4M4)/n$, M1-M4 represents the number of cells with one to four nuclei, respectively, and n indicates the number of cells scored.

Conclusion

The study revealed that β -asarone was not genotoxic for the tested dose in human peripheral blood lymphocytes.

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